

PRESERVING OUR HEALTH: A COMMON HERITAGE

To pool health knowledge and technologies ensures better care,
divides costs and creates local employment.

Listening to plural realities in health allows us to humanise care,
and to build resilience in the face of crises.

20 testimonials, festival 'taking care together'

The united hearts illustrate the listening and commoning of pluralist feelings, the cohabitation across knowledge systems.

The clover calls to harmony between Nature and our deepest nature. Rare and humble, the four-lobed clover incites joy and happiness.

The colours, emerging from shadow, invite us to reveal what is not visible.

inclusive approaches that strengthen our collective and individual capacities to take care

... rather than universalist techniques which desolidarise us

- pluralist contributions from field actors and pioneering researchers
- dialogue enhancing cohabitation between systems of knowledges
- exclusion of profit-aimed projects

- strengthening the inclusion of vulnerabilised, poor visible communities
- sharing stories which unify
- making links between themes (body-mind-consciousness)

a co-creation based on introspection, active listening and the ability to reach agreement

... rather than measures imposed which dehumanise us

- program resulting from the convergence of pluralist realities
- format that values sustained personal commitment
- "out of doors" event to recharge our batteries in contact with nature

- #### FUTURE
- refining our "method of emergence" for societal challenges (popular consensus)
 - encouraging the self-organization of similar citizen events
 - making research and events mutually supportive

new knowledge generated by citizens, which are freely accessible and enrichables

... rather than innovations which profits benefit to a minority

- quantified voluntary contributions
- documented exchanges on mediawiki, in video and podcast
- heritage disseminated under a free/libre licence, in editable format and open standard, if possible

- developing a web platform for pooling resources for our health (econ. of scale)
- constituting a foundation to maintain the co-created heritage in the long-term
- removing barriers to access contributions: literacy, languages, ...

This festival is an invitation to explore how we can reclaim our health and define together the rules that affect us. It is about recognising that, when we are together, we have the resources and abilities to ensure every human can live in dignity.

Fabio Balli

FREE / LIBRE TECHNOLOGIES IN HEALTH

OPENVILLAGE.CH 2020

Today, one human out of two lacks access to essential medical care. Despite this, medical expenses have increased by 17% in 15 years. Pooling the design of medical equipment can improve access to qualitative care and encourage the creation of local jobs.

When I saw the video of a carpenter and a costume designer collaborating and designing 3D printable fingers, I **proposed a map. People who wanted or needed to make hands put pins in them.** The social and psychological function of prostheses is at least as important as the medical, mechanical one. One child said: "I have a funny hand and have bad dreams. Monsters are chasing me. But now I turn to them and say, 'You don't scare me because I have two hands!'" This child had not yet received his prosthesis...

Jon Schull, USA

Open source offers many possibilities for medtech: we can talk about quality of devices, harmonisation of standards, education, but also **create savings by producing locally.** German health system could save 200 million € per year by open-sourcing MRI scanners. And we could export these technologies to countries where they are even more needed. For example, there are 125 MRIs in Berlin, 26 in Spain, and two in Senegal, for a much larger population. It determines whether you get a good diagnosis and how long will it take.

Lukas Winter, Germany

I introduced the alcohol-based hand sanitizer. The advantage of a product without a patent is that anyone can produce it, even in poor countries. **Having a lot of projects is very good... at the beginning.** People should pool their energy and collective intelligence to produce devices which can become accessible everywhere in the world, and also easy to repair, easy to manufacture with components that can be found anywhere.

Didier Pittet, Switzerland

I was surprised that the cost of designing drugs rises from millions to billions, while sequencing the genome decreases from 300 million to little. Design is done in silos, without involving young people. **Today, before being manufactured, a plane is flown, crashed and landed on a computer.** We then designed a computer model in systems biology. We mobilised 12,000 students to synthesise 50,000 articles, and decided that the software would be entirely open-source. 8,700 researchers from 130 countries have contributed. **We discovered that a diabetes drug can treat tuberculosis,** a neglected disease that kills 4,000 people a day..

Samir Brahmachari, India

HEALTH COMMONS

OPENVILLAGE.CH 2022

Peer production of freely reproducible medical material was discussed in 2022 as well.
Gathering with makers and researchers.

When Wikipedia started, the big encyclopaedias laughed: "How can citizens make an encyclopaedia, a thing for scholars? Besides, it's full of mistakes". And Wikipedia replied: "Yes, but it takes us six months to correct a mistake, while you need 25 to 30 years. And the end of the story: Britannica went bankrupt, Universalis went bankrupt.

Benjamin Coriat, economist

In 2020, we did our quarantine in the fab lab: maybe we could make useful things. The first idea was face shields. There was a lot of interest. As there were about 20 of us, we could not meet all the demands. So we put our designs on open-source and activated 42 cities. We managed to produce one million units in 49 days, what the industry could not. Then we produced oxygen concentrators. This time we had 150 organisations doing open research. We were able to go from zero knowledge to manufacturing within eight weeks!

Richa Shrivastava, engineer

LISTENING MEDICINE

OPENVILLAGE.CH 2022

How to take care of the relationship between patients and caregivers?
How to value the subjective experience of patients and caregivers?
How to reduce inequalities and abuses of power in care environments?
Gathering with philosophers and ethicists.

While travelling, I felt that a painful crisis was coming. Once in the hospital, I found myself in front of caregivers who did not know sickle cell disease, who did not consider my request (despite a medical chip implanted). I had a cardiorespiratory arrest because of this. Medicine is political, it is a power struggle. **We as patients have to gain enough power to get what we need.** I think that many patients die because they are not listened to.

David-Zacharie Issom, IT specialist

Medical students were asked to write a story about a patient who made an impression on them. The intern, in a resuscitation internship in the middle of covid, wrote "I cannot write about a patient who made an impression on me, because I followed 21 patients, and all 21 died". She said this with such emotion that everyone cried. And instead of saying "We'll talk about it", no, the dialogue is cut off, it is closed right away. There is a lot of work to be done among medical studies...

Laurine Omnès, philosopher

PRESERVING OUR MENTAL HEALTH

OPENVILLAGE.CH 2022

How to recover when living in a situation of mental vulnerability?
How to regain dignity and autonomy as the weeks go by?
How can the harms of exclusion be reduced?
Gathering with peer helpers and directors from psycho-social sector.

As a person affected by addiction, what I discovered when I started to recover, from the moment I acknowledged who I am when I use, what I become, and what I cannot be, is that I did not always know what was good for me. Because the disease somewhere took over. I was lucky enough to meet good therapists, and this process only worked when I really realised that there was a part of me that wasn't damaged, and that it was going to help me out of years of suffering.

Tania Zambrano Ovalle, peer practitioner

Psychiatry is the only medical speciality that can inject treatments by force. To ignore a refusal means de facto to assimilate the mind to a chemical substance whose reaction can be accurately predicted depending to the applied treatment. This is to forget the meta-physical nature of suffering, of the feeling of freedom, of the study of symptoms!

Fabien Coronado, peer helper

OUR PLANET, OUR HEALTH

OPENVILLAGE.CH 2022

What are the links between the destruction of biodiversity and the increase in diseases?
Which lifestyles and socio-economic models should we adopt to preserve our planetary health?
Gathering with nurses, doctors, engineers and researchers.

There is a struggle concerning which way humanity should go, and I think there is the real debate. **Understanding that our five senses do not allow us to feel the seriousness of the situation** seems important to me. There can be an erosion of biological diversity and landscape would still look green under the sun. A change in behaviour cannot happen till we have not shared the reason for the change. The health of the Earth and our health go hand in hand.

René Longet, sustainability expert

Biodiversity is our common home. If we destroy the common home, we cannot survive... And we are rowing because, among other things, there is too much proximity between politicians and those who have an interest in maintaining the system as it is.

Marie-Monique Robin, film director

WALKSHOPS

Exchanges facilitated during a two-hour walk along the banks of the wild Rhône river, followed by a pooling of ideas. Themes: eco-anxiety, listening, social participation, Geneva medical ecosystem, commons, decolonisation. Gathering with researchers and employees of international organisations.

Geneva is a great city if you wish to walk. The countryside is close to the city, with beautiful landscapes. I like this way of interacting because it is a safe way to meet strangers, to share thoughts and feelings. This is what we have missed so much during last two years. I think it's really time to reconnect.

Bruno Meessen, economist

I liked the thematic walk in the forest and its "hidden" principle: walking, being careful not to fall, all this gave more spontaneous answers. It was very round-communication, more fluid, freer than around a round table: everyone could talk, could talk to others! We left separately, but the small groups were able to exchange during a break at the water's edge, before the thematic return to the large group. Very nice, rich and sincere sharing!

David Risse, sociologist

“LEGISLATIVE THEATRE”

Staging of three situations of oppression in order to face them together, and to propose legislative changes
Topics: burnout among caregivers, patients' rights and medical violence, restriction of fundamental freedoms
Gathering with actors and lawyers.

What stood out for me was the investment of the audience, especially people who have a disability, who are racialised, who have a chronic illness, or who live in these intersections. To me, making law together makes a difference, because we can be subjects-actors of these situations. We have experienced something transformational, because there has been a decompartmentalisation between the legal and civil society. The law has been put back in its right place: it has empowered people.

Meloe Gennai, lawyer

The importance of being alive is the harmony between the body, the mind, and of course the consciousness. It only takes one person in the world, who has the courage to be, just to be. My energy is enough to change the world, I can radiate around me, the opening of the heart. We can explore new worlds together, we connect to the cosmos. What makes us happy is to see others happy. Overcoming oneself is possible when we are inspired by the people around us.

Isabelle Wachsmuth, engineer

ARTS FOR HEALING

OPENVILLAGE.CH 2022

Art allows us to express our inner world beyond words, and to recognise the resources that lie dormant within us. Gathering with therapists through the arts.

What I particularly like about Geneva is the opportunity to meet children and adults from different cultures, talking different languages. At the end of the day, we share something in common, which is art. It does not matter which language you speak, because art has the power to unite people. You don't have to have a serious problem to try Art Therapy: it is a magical way to feel better, to discover yourself and to enjoy it.

Vicky Tsiaousi, art therapist

I will tell the story of a cultural prescriptions for a lady at the end of her life, who no longer speaks. I propose her a palette of perfumes that allow her to soothe, to glow, to sparkle. You can sparkle until the end of your life. Her daughter says "My mum would like the love rose". I put the perfume on a stick and she inhales. And there I had the impression that the daughter was playing the cello with her mother, making music with the perfume. And this mother starts to cry. Then she looks me straight in the eyes, and with a childlike look, she smiles at me. And then her daughter starts to cry. And I say "Why are you crying? And she replies, "Because my mother hasn't cried, hasn't smiled, for so long".

Laure Mayoud, psychologist

SHARING CIRCLES

A time to take care of oneself...
A time to take care of each other...
Gatherings with neighbours in Bernex,
Châtillens, Geneva, Vernier, Villeneuve.

Futuristic workshop

Artistic workshop

Ancestral Circle of Senegal

Let's imagine together
a new scenario

Ancestral Circle of Syria

Let us regenerate
human
consciousness
together

We become aware that our emotions can heal us:
seeing beauty every morning,
hearing a bird singing, seeing a painting,
listening to music, reading a beautiful book.
I would love it if the scientific community
would integrate emotions to find solutions.
Our body has all the tools to heal.

Julie Abissegue, curator

Roundtable on Beauty

Eco-stress and Psyche

Healing collectives

The art of being alive

Making commons
to take care of the world

IMPACT

500 PARTICIPANTS
158 CONTRIBUTORS

500,000 FRANCS OF COLLECTIVE VALUE
7,800 HOURS OF CONTRIBUTIONS

leadership ●●●
Breathing Games Association

patronage ●
Geneva Health Forum
Open Geneva

financial support ●
a genevan foundation
Fondation Leenaards
Fondation Lunt

co-hosts ●●●
Fondation de l'Orme
Association re-pairs
Systmd
Alliance Santé Planétaire
Association Aura
WHO ●
APSAT
ARAET

co-organisation ●●
AddictLab Academy
CERN
Collège de Rétablissement
CReACC-Diversités
DNDi
EchOpen

Geneva eLab
IdeaVox
L'Art d'être vivant
La Main Tendue Genève
Le Caméléon
LogAir
Maker's Asylum

Mamajah
Minds
Nuit Blanche
NVC Geneva
Open Data
Radio Libre
SDG Solution Space
University of Geneva ●

LET'S MEET ON

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10 MEDIA INTERVIEWS

101 WIKI P.

30 VIDEOS